

Preparation, Characterization and Evaluation of Ramipril Loaded Solid Lipid Nanoparticles for Improved Bioavailability

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Abstract:

Purpose: Ramipril is a potential antihypertensive drug employed in the management of hypertension and its oral bioavailability 28%. The intent of the work to evolve solid lipid nanoparticles of ramipril for enhancement of bioavailability.

Methods: The SLNs of ramipril were developed by hot homogenization followed by ultrasonication technique. Lipids are dynasan 114, dynasan 116, dynasan 114, imwitor 900 P. Non ionic surfactants are poloxamer 188, polysorbate 80 and lipoid E 80 act as an amphoteric stabilizing agent is used to synthesize solid lipid nanoparticles of sumatriptan succinate.

Results: Developed ramipril SLNs have shown the mean size of particles are 234-412 nm, Zeta potential values varied from -18.4 ± 0.782 to -42.2 ± 1.571 mV which indicated stability of developed ramipril solid lipid nanoparticles. Entrapment efficiency of formulations found between 94% and 99%. SLNs of ramipril were established likely spherical with a lustrous exterior, as examine making do with scanning electron microscope (SEM). The compatibility of drug with excipients was ascertained through differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). The bioavailability research considerations were carried out on male wistar rats, the innovative preparation of ramipril SLNs and coarse suspension administered by oral route.

Conclusion: Relative bioavailability of developed formulation of SLNs of dynasan 114 and combination of poloxamer 188 and polysorbate 80 ramipril (F9) was increased by 1.35 times differentiated with the reference standard coarse suspension.

Keywords: *Bioavailability, solid lipid nanoparticles, homogenization and ramipril.*

Introduction

Hypertension is a growing global problem that is associated with numerous underlying pathophysiological conditions (Hu, et al., 2002). These include ventricular hypertrophy,

endothelial dysfunction, metabolic syndrome, a procoagulant state, oxidative stress, inflammation and a genetic predisposition to cardiovascular events (Harde, Das, & Jain, 2011).

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Hypertension is a growing global problem that is associated with numerous underlying pathophysiological conditions (Hu, et al., 2002). These include ventricular hypertrophy, endothelial dysfunction, metabolic syndrome, a procoagulant state, oxidative stress, inflammation and a genetic predisposition to cardiovascular events (Harde, Das, & Jain, 2011).

Hypertension is a growing global problem that is associated with numerous underlying pathophysiological conditions. The treatment of hypertension disease by angiotensin converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitors is first choice of drugs. The hypertensive patients need adequately small doses (2.5 to 10 mg/day) which are well accepted (Delie, & Blanco-Príeto, 2005).

The therapeutic efficacy of drug is depending on drug concentration. The drug shows low concentration it leads to therapeutic failure of drug due to first pass effect, poor solubility, low bioavailability and high fluctuation of plasma. A pioneering assuring design to defeat these distinguished difficulties by the advancement of appropriate colloidal carrier approaches. Encompassed by the carrier methods have lot of benefits and limited obstacles of solid lipid nanoparticles as correlated to variant carrier methods (Mukherjee, Ray, & Thakur, 2009).

Solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs) know a substitute to colloidal techniques like liposome (by using phospholipids), noisome (non-ionic surfactants) and polymeric nanoparticles. SLNs comprises of essentially solid lipids, which represent as a stabilizer when diffuse in water in the sight of a surfactant. SLN is pertaining to its nano size, higher surface area and extensive drug loading proportions. In the same manner, it promotes drug consistency and has the potential to enhance the oral bioavailability of water insoluble drugs (Garud, Singh, & Garud, 2012).

Ramipril is a highly significant orally long lasting angiotension converting enzyme inhibitor. The potent metabolite of ramipril is a ramiprilat and act as a reversible inhibitor. Ramipril decreases blood pressure in distinctive models of hypertension and ameliorates modes of acute heart failure mainly by constraint of angiotensin

II production (Pardeike, Hommoss, & Müller, 2009).

The key objective of the existent research work was to scale up solid lipid nanoparticles of ramipril, to avoid the pre-systemic metabolism and to enhance its oral bioavailability of ramipril. The oral bioavailability of ramipril is 28% and it is rapidly eliminated through renal pathway (Müller, Radtke, & Wissing, 2002). It is lipophilic nature (log P 3.32) and water insoluble drug. On the basis of the above characteristics of drug, it is suitable to develop the solid lipid nanoparticles of ramipril.

Materials and Methods

Materials

Ramipril hydrochloride was acquired as a gift sample from Lupine pharmaceutical industries, Aurangabad, India. Trimyristin was procured from Hi Media Labs, Mumbai. Tristearin was obtained from Sigma Aldrich, Hyderabad. Lipoid E80 was procured from Lipoid, Germany respectively. Poloxamer 188 was gift samples from Aurobindo Labs, India. Polysorbate 60 was obtained from Rankem, Chennai. Methanol and chloroform were of HPLC grade Merck, Mumbai.

Development of Ramipril Solid Lipid Nanoparticles

The ramipril solid lipid nanoparticles were developed by using homogenization accompanied by ultrasonication technique. Ramipril (drug 10mg), solid lipid (50/100/150/required quantity mg) and lipoid E80 (100mg) were liquefied in 20 mL combination of chloroform and methanol (1:1). The organic solvents were separated by rota evaporator (Heidolph, Germany) Drug encapsulated lipid covering layer was molten by heating system at 5°C over melting point of lipid used in formulation. The aqueous phase was developed by using surfactants were poloxamer (Pluronic) 188 and polysorbate 80. These surfactants dissolving in double distilled water and heated to the similar temperature of oil phase. The hot aqueous phase was added to oil

phase, and submitted to homogenization cycle process was conducted (at 12,000 rpm) by using homogenizer for the period of 5min. Coarse heated oil in water (O/W) emulsion attained was ultra sonicated (Bandelin, Germany) for 20min. Ramipril loaded solid lipid nanoparticles were

developed by permitting heated nanoemulsion to cool to room temperature (Ekambaram, & Abdul, 2011).

The diverse formulations components are presented in below Table 1.

Table 1. Formulation of Solid Lipid Nanoparticles (SLNs) of Ramipril

Formulation ingredients (mg)	Formulation Codes											
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10	F11	F12
Organic phase												
Ramipril	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Dynasan 118	50	100	150	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Dynasan 116	-	-	-	50	100	150	-	-	-	-	-	-
Dynasan 114	-	-	-	-	-	-	50	100	150	-	-	-
Imwitor 900P	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	50	100	150
Lipoid E 80	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Chloroform:Methanol (1:1) (mL)	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20
Aqueous phase												
Poloxamer 188 (Pluronic F 68)	25	50	75	25	50	75	25	50	75	25	50	75
Polysorbate 60	75	50	25	75	50	25	75	50	25	75	50	25
Double distilled water (mL)	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10

Characterizations of Ramipril Solid Lipid Nanoparticles

A) Determination of particle size, PDI and zeta potential of SLNs of ramipril

The mean size of particles and zeta potential of ramipril loaded solid lipid nano particles were measured by employing a Malvern Zetasizer (Nano ZS90). The developed ramipril solid lipid nano particles were 100µl was diluted to 5mL with help of double distilled water to achieve ideal kilo counts per second (KCPS) of 50-200 for measurements. The zeta potential of the diluted dispersion of solid lipid nanoparticles was determined by using Malvern Zetasizer (Nano ZS90) (Uner, & Yener, 2007).

B) Surface morphology studies by SEM Analysis

The surface appearance of developed ramipril SLNs formulations was ascertained by SEM (Scanning Electron Microscope-Hitachi200, Japan). The earlier examination, the formulated samples were fixed on a double adhesive carbon tape, which was stuck on aluminum stubs and then covered with gold beneath an argon

atmosphere. The samples of solid lipid nanoparticles of ramipril were analyzed in scanning electron microscope under high vacuum of 40kv (Mulla, et al., 2011).

C) Determination of Drug content

About 0.1 ml of ramipril solid lipid nanoparticles preparation were collected and diluted pertinent with chloroform: methanol (1:1) and then determine the drug content of diluted samples were examined by HPLC procedure at λ_{max} 210 nm.

D) Determination of Entrapment efficiency

Entrapment efficiency of developed formulations was certainty by assessing the concentration of free drug (unentrapped) in the aqueous phase. The aqueous phase was partitioned by ultra filtration utilising centrivot tubes which be composed of a filter membrane (MWCO 20kDa) at the base of the test sample regeneration chamber, was placed on the topmost of sample and centrifuged around at 4000 rpm for the time period of 30 min. The developed ramipril solid lipid nanoparticles assisting with the encasing drug stay on in

exterior chamber and the aqueous phase transferred into sample recovery chamber done with filter membrane. The appropriate amount of ramipril in aqueous solution phase was predicted by HPLC technique (Mehnert, & Mäder, 2001).

E) *In vitro* studies for ramipril solid lipid nanoparticles

The *in vitro* release of SLNs ramipril was executed using dialysis technique. Dialysis membrane having adequate pore size 2.4nm and the molecular weight cut off within 12,000 to 14,000 was used for the release studies and dialysis membrane was immersed overnight in double distilled water. The drug release studies of developed formulations were carried out successively for first 2 hours in 0.1N HCl, subsequently by using pH6.8 in phosphate buffer for 24 hours by open tube approach. In which dialysis membrane fixed to open tube (contained SLNs ramipril dispersion) as donor compartment and buffer (100mL) containing 200mL beaker as receptor compartment and the required temperature was maintained at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$, 2mL sample was withdrawn at the different time interval sampling points of 0.25, 0.5, 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12 and 24 hours from receiver compartment and replaced with equal proportion of fresh buffer. The drug release samples were collected, then diluted appropriately and examined by UV-Visible spectrophotometer at λ_{max} 210 nm using the relevant receptor medium as a blank, to find out the extent of drug released from the solid lipid nanoparticles of ramipril (Hu, et al., 2002).

Pharmacokinetic Study

Animals

Healthy male Wister rats (weighing 200-230gm) were exploited for the pharmacokinetic study of developed formulation. The animals were starved overnight and had available access to water. The animal studies were carried out with earlier acceptance of Institutional Animal Ethical Committee (Reg. No: 10/IAEC/CCPER/CPCSEA/2022).

Study protocol

The animals were separate into two groups (n=6) and were orally administered with developed formulation (F9) of ramipril SLNs and coarse suspension (marketed tablet make into suspension form) at a dose level of 8mg/kg body weight. All the formulations were administered orally with the rat oral feeding tube.

Group 1: Developed solid lipid nanoparticles of ramipril (F9)

Group 2: Coarse suspension (Marketed tablet-Ramistar, Manufactured by-Lupin Ltd)

At suitable specified time intervals after oral administration, blood samples were collected at different time interval points (0, 0.5, 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 18, 24 and 30 hours) by retro-orbital venous plexus puncture method. The blood samples were permitted to clot and centrifuged for 10min at 14000 rpm. The serum was isolated and conveyed into clean micro centrifuge tubes and stored at -20°C until HPLC studies (Harde, Das, & Jain, 2011).

Chromatographic Conditions of Ramipril in Rat Serum by HPLC

Mobile phase: Methanol: Potassium dihydrogen ortho phosphate buffer (65:35).

Column specifications: C_{18} (250 mm X 4.6 mm i.d., 5 μm)

UV-detection at: 210nm

Detector sensitivity: 1.0000 AUFS

Injection volume: 20 μl

Retention time: 12.10 min

A) Extraction studies of rat serum samples consisting of ramipril

To 100 μL of serum, 100 μl of internal standard (Enalapril 5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$) and 100 μl of methanol were introduced. Subsequent to vortex stirring for 10 min at room temperature, the samples were centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 15 min. After centrifugation the whole organic layer was isolated and moved into another micro centrifuge tube and then evaporated under reduced pressure in a vacuum oven. The residue was reconstituted with 100 μl of mobile phase.

Finally, a volume of 20 μL reconstituted sample was injected into the HPLC system for studies (Chirio, et al., 2011).

B) Calculation of pharmacokinetic parameters

The concentration of solid lipid nanoparticles ramipril in rat serum samples were attained from the calibration curve prepared. The pharmacokinetic parameters like C_{max} , T_{max} , AUC and $t_{1/2}$ were measured by kinetica (2000) software (Olbrich, Kayser, & Müller, 2002). The relative bioavailability of the developed formulations was determined based on following equation:

$$\% \text{ Relative BA} = \frac{\text{AUC}_{\text{SLN}} \times \text{Dose control}}{\text{AUC control} \times \text{Dose}^{\text{SLN}}} \times 100$$

Figure 1. DSC thermogram of pure form of Ramipril Drug

B) DSC thermograms of physical mixtures of drug and different lipids

The physical blend of drug and dynasan 118 produced extensive and sharpened endothermic peaks around at 76.19°C and 123.86°C, consecutively. The physical blend of drug and dynasan 116 exhibited intense sharp endothermic peaks at 176.89°C and 288.98°C, successively. The physical blend of drug and

Results and Discussion

Drug and Excipient Compatibility Studies

A) Determination of purity of the drug by Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) studies were acclimated to find out the presence of any interaction between drug and the excipients and also to find out any changes in the crystallinity of the drug. Physical mixtures of lipids and ramipril (1:1 mass/molar ratio) were prepared and filled crucibles about 5-10mg. Analysis were performed under a nitrogen purge. The heating rate was maintained at 10°C/min and the produced thermograms were examined for any type of interaction (Narala, & Veerabrahma, 2013). The DSC thermogram of ramipril (Fig.1) showed a sharp endothermic peak at 109.35°C which corresponds to the melting point of ramipril which indicates crystalline nature of drug. The DSC studies help to assess the interaction of different components of the formulation.

dynasan 114 exhibited sharp endothermic peaks at 54.59°C and 289.44°C, consecutively. The physical blend of drug and imwitor 900 P showed sharp endothermic peaks at 180.41°C and 306.13°C. The peaks are associated to drug are viewed at rightward of thermogram and lipid allied peaks are on leftward of thermogram (Xie, et al., 2011). The DSC thermograms of physical blend of drug and lipids figures are (Figure 2) represented below.

a) Dynasan118 and Ramipril

b) Dynasan 116 and Ramipril

c) Dynasan114 and Ramipril

d) Imwitor 900P and Ramipril

Figure 2 (a-d). DSC Thermograms of Physical Blend of Drug and Different Lipids

C) Drug characterization by FTIR

The consistency within the drug and lipids was correlated by using FT-IR spectra. The position point of peak in FT-IR spectra of pure form of ramipril is differentiated with those in FT-IR spectra of ramipril plus other excipients. It was ascertained that, present was no eclipse or shift in peak orientation place of ramipril in any FT-IR spectra of drug and excipients, which established that drug and excipients were compatible. As a result, it seemingly finalized that drug can be adapted with the selected lipids

in formulation without influencing instability in the formulation of ramipril SLNs (Garcia-Fuentes, Torres, & Alonso, 2005).

Determination of Particle Size, PDI, Zeta Potential, Drug Content and Entrapment Efficiency of Ramipril Loaded SLNs (n=3)

All the developed formulations were studied in sequence to influence their particle size distribution, zeta potential (ZP), polydispersity index (PDI) values, drug content and entrapment efficiency. The results pertaining to

optimized formulation (F9) of particle size along with PDI value and zeta potential values are shown in figure. 4, 5 & 6, respectively (Hu, et al., 2010). The zeta potential, particle size distribution, entrapment efficiency (EE) and drug content of the SLNs of ramipril were

determined. The polydispersity indices were within the permissible range (below 0.3) for developed formulations. The average particle size of ramipril SLNs was found to be 200-350nm. The expected outcomes are stated in below the Table 2.

Table 2. Size, PDI, Zeta Potential, Drug Content and Entrapment Efficiency of Varying Formulations

Formulation code	Size (nm)	PDI $\pm$ SD	Zeta potential (mv) $\pm$ SD	Drug content (mg) $\pm$ SD	Entrapment efficiency (%) $\pm$ SD
F1	291.3 $\pm$ 4.41	0.126 $\pm$ 0.03	-32.4 $\pm$ 1.42	9.79 $\pm$ 0.015	98.75 $\pm$ 0.008
F2	316.4 $\pm$ 4.10	0.153 $\pm$ 0.06	-30 $\pm$ 1.26	9.91 $\pm$ 0.01	97.64 $\pm$ 0.005
F3	234.9 $\pm$ 6.53	0.156 $\pm$ 0.05	-28.3 $\pm$ 1.48	10.01 $\pm$ 0.06	94.17 $\pm$ 0.002
F4	262.2 $\pm$ 4.47	0.208 $\pm$ 0.11	-28.9 $\pm$ 1.79	10.00 $\pm$ 0.10	98.91 $\pm$ 0.012
F5	286 $\pm$ 1.527	0.252 $\pm$ 0.031	-24.2 $\pm$ 1.289	10.0 $\pm$ 0.051	99.71 $\pm$ 0.46
F6	402 $\pm$ 0.577	0.277 $\pm$ 0.010	-18.4 $\pm$ 0.782	8.92 $\pm$ 0.10	99.42 $\pm$ 0.026
F7	225.1 $\pm$ 0.608	0.219 $\pm$ 0.013	-31.7 $\pm$ 0.650	9.56 $\pm$ 0.17	99.10 $\pm$ 0.020
F8	257 $\pm$ 2.08	0.171 $\pm$ 0.048	-29.9 $\pm$ 0.897	11.01 $\pm$ 0.062	98.65 $\pm$ 0.035
F9	264 $\pm$ 1.00	0.210 $\pm$ 0.05	-22.5 $\pm$ 1.635	10.02 $\pm$ 0.20	99.71 $\pm$ 0.8
F10	391 $\pm$ 1.74	0.272 $\pm$ 0.021	-42.2 $\pm$ 1.571	10.5 $\pm$ 0.032	98.84 $\pm$ 0.94
F11	412 $\pm$ 1.527	0.259 $\pm$ 0.031	-38.7 $\pm$ 1.489	10.8 $\pm$ 0.047	96.75 $\pm$ 0.46
F12	325 $\pm$ 2.216	0.261 $\pm$ 0.028	-31.2 $\pm$ 1.352	9.6 $\pm$ 0.071	95.49 $\pm$ 0.18

Figure 3. Ramipril SLNs formulations: A) PDI and B) Particle Size that should be Reversed

The zeta potential of developed formulations containing ramipril SLNs was in the extent of -42 mV to -18 mV. The formulations containing dynasan 118 showed particle size ranging from 234 to 316nm, PDI 0.126 to 0.156, and Zeta potential -28.3 to -32.4 mV respectively. SLN

formulation containing dynasan 116 showed particle size ranging from 262 to 402nm, PDI 0.208 to 0.277, and Zeta potential -18.4 to -28.9mV respectively. SLN formulation containing dynasan 114 showed particle size ranging from 225 to 264nm, PDI 0.171 to 0.231,

and Zeta potential -20.9 to -32.5 mV respectively. SLNs formulation containing imwitor 900 P showed particle size ranging from 325 to 412nm, PDI 0.259 to 0.272, Zeta potential -31.2 to -42.2 mV. Entrapment efficiency of all the developed formulations (F1-F12) was estimated be 94.17 to 99.10% and drug content were determined and there is no remarkable difference is observed between in drug content & entrapment efficiency was noticed.

The particle size of ramipril SLNs was depends on alkyl chain extent of lipids, higher alkyl chain length higher the particle size. The external

surface charge is an essential role to maintain the stability of colloidal dispersion. The particles having smaller particle size having more stability of solid lipid nanoparticles. The surfactant poloxamer 188 was used in the formulation, belongs to a non ionic surfactant and lowered the electrostatic repulsion among the particles following sterical stabilization of the nanoparticles by producing a coat over their surface for maintaining the stability of SLNs. The developed formulations containing dynasan 114 (F9) exhibited relatively more remarkable size, PDI and ZP when differentiated to other formulations (Khan, et al., 2012; Suresh, et al., 2007).

Figure 4. Zeta Potential of Optimized Ramipril SLNs Formulation (F9)

Figure 5. Particle Size Distribution of Optimized Ramipril SLNs Formulation (F9)

Cumulative % Drug Release of SLNs by Dialysis Method

Formulations containing dynasan 118, dynasan 116, dynasan 114 and imwitor 900 P exhibited drug release extending from 64.28 to 78.15%, and 73.12 to 85.13%, 82.19 to 91.61% and 79.15

to 84.18% respectively for initial study conducted in 2 h in 0.1N HCl then subsequently by 6.8 pH phosphate buffer up to 24 h (Fig 7). The developed formulation F9 *in vitro* drug release was determined to be 91.61% in 24 h and release of drug in sustained manner. The increased lipid content in formulations gradually;

the release of drug was considerably prolonged in all the developed SLNs formulations of ramipril. Further, all SLNs formulations released to a certain extent gradually when compared to that of coarse suspension of ramipril (Ramistar). All the developed formulations were carried out in triplicate (n=3).

The *in vitro* release pattern of all developed ramipril SLNs formulations presented a

conventional biphasic arrangement with a primary expeditive phase accompanied by a slow phase release pattern observed in phosphate buffer. The primary rapid phase is able to because of the burst release of drug. An obtainable assertion is a tiny diffusion path caused by adornment of drug in the outer region of SLNs on the exterior surface of solid (Yang, et al., 1999)

Figure 7. Cumulative % Drug Release from Prepared Ramipril Solid Lipid Nanoparticles

Stability Studies

Ramipril loaded SLNs were preserved at room and refrigerated temperature for the period of 60 days and characteristic size of particles, zeta potential and poly dispersity indices were

studied. The ramipril SLNs stability studies were assisted for formulation (F9) which produced more effective size, PDI and zeta potential. The number of samples predicted was in triplicate (n=3) (Amir Kalvanagh, et al., 2019).

Table 3. Stability Studies of Optimized Formulation (F9) at Both Room Temperature (25°C) and Refrigerated (4°C) for a Period 2 Months

Day	At room temperature			At refrigerated temperature		
	Size (nm)	PDI	Zeta potential (mV)	Size (nm)	PDI	Zeta potential (mV)
1	264.1±6.53	0.272±0.05	-22.5±1.38	265.9±6.53	0.279±0.05	-22.3±1.38
30	271.5±5.45	0.281±0.14	-21.3±2.06	274.5±6.54	0.285±0.12	-23.1±2.36
60	278.9±6.49	0.289±0.06	-18.9±2.08	279.9±5.59	0.291±0.09	-24.5±2.48

There was no considerable difference found in sizes and zeta potentials of the optimized formulation (F9) during two months storage at

room temperature at 25° C and refrigerated at 4°C.

Pharmacokinetic Study

The pharmacokinetic parameters of ramipril in distinctive rats for two formulations (coarse suspension (Ramistar) and developed ramipril SLNs formulation, F9) were determined by non compartmental conceptions by using through Kinetica 2000 software. The pharmacokinetic parameters like, AUC, C_{max}, T_{max}, MRT and t_{1/2} were attained for optimized ramipril SLNs formulation and differentiated with that of coarse suspension of ramistar marketed product. The results different pharmacokinetic parameters calculated and stated in below table 4. Based on results, it was found that ramipril SLNs (F9) exhibited high C_{max} and AUC values when distinguished to coarse suspension.

The bioavailability of optimized ramipril SLNs relative to higher than that of the coarse suspension. This is due to either enhancing surface area of drug available for release, which would increase the aqueous solubility of drug. When compared, administering the ramipril SLNs and coarse suspension, there was 1.35 fold increases in relative bioavailability to the coarse suspension. Therefore, by developing ramipril SLNs formulation oral bioavailability could be enhanced shown in fig 8.

Table 4. Pharmacokinetic parameters of ramipril SLNs and coarse suspension

Parameter	Optimized ramipril SLN (F9)	Coarse suspension
C _{max} ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	248.678 $\pm$ 12.7***	193.89 $\pm$ 1.58
T _{max} (hr)	2	2
AUC ($\mu\text{g/mL}\cdot\text{h}$)	2972.259 $\pm$ 248.4**	2168.34 $\pm$ 43.14
T _{1/2} (hr)	8.43 $\pm$ 1.8**	7.29 $\pm$ 0.46
MRT	13.70 $\pm$ 1.8**	12.02 $\pm$ 0.48

Note: ***significance, **less significance

The AUC of developed (F9) increased by 1.35 fold when compared to coarse suspension.

Figure 8. Pharmacokinetic Profile of Developed SLNs of Ramipril (F9) and Coarse Suspension in Rat Serum and by Oral Administration

Statistical Analysis of Pharmacokinetic Data for Ramipril SLNs Formulation

Statistical testing of pharmacokinetic data of developed ramipril SLNs formulation (F9) and coarse suspension were performed. Unpaired t-test was done using graph pad prism software (version8.0) at a significance level of p-value <0.05. Hence, the development of ramipril SLNs formulation (F9) is advantageous over coarse suspension to improve solubility, dissolution and subsequently bioavailability.

Conclusion

The poor absorption of ramipril was enhanced by formulating into ramipril SLNs with the use of lipids. SLNs were prepared with dynasan 118, dynasan 116, dynasan 114, and imwitor 900 P, further examined for particle size, zeta potential, PDI, drug content, entrapment efficiency of drug and *in vitro* release studies. The *in vitro* release studies were executed for ramipril SLNs for first 2h in 0.1N HCl subsequently by 24h in pH 6.8 phosphate buffer. SLNs of ramipril showed prolonged manner of drug release. SLNs of dynasan 114 loaded with ramipril were prepared with a surfactant (poloxamer 188 and polysorbate 80), forming a stabilizing layer over the solid lipid nanoparticles. The ramipril SLNs formulation (F9) showed good zeta potential

and particle size. Current study of this work that SLNs carrier may help for enhance the bioavailability of ramipril for treatment of hypertension. The fabricated formulation (F9) showed 1.35 folds increased in relative bioavailability compared to the coarse suspension in pharmacokinetic study were performed in male wistar rats.

References

- Amir Kalvanagh, P., Ebtokara, M., Kokhaei, P., & Soleimanjahi, H. (2019). Preparation and Characterization of PLGA Nanoparticles Containing Plasmid DNA Encoding Human IFN-lambda-1/IL-29. *Iranian journal of pharmaceutical research : IJPR*, 18(1), 156–167.
- Chirio, D., Gallarate, M., Peira, E., Battaglia, L., Serpe, L., & Trotta, M. (2011). Formulation of curcumin-loaded solid lipid nanoparticles produced by fatty acids coacervation technique. *Journal of microencapsulation*, 28(6), 537–548. <https://doi.org/10.3109/02652048.2011.590615>
- Delie, F., & Blanco-Prieto, M. J. (2005). Polymeric particulates to improve oral bioavailability of peptide drugs. *Molecules (Basel, Switzerland)*, 10(1), 65–80. <https://doi.org/10.3390/10010065>
- Ekambaram, P., & Abdul, H. S. (2011). Formulation and evaluation of solid lipid nanoparticles of ramipril. *Journal of young pharmacists : JYP*, 3(3), 216–220. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0975-1483.83765>
- Garcia-Fuentes, M., Torres, D., & Alonso, M. J. (2005). New surface-modified lipid nanoparticles as delivery vehicles for salmon calcitonin. *International journal of pharmaceuticals*, 296(1-2), 122–132. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpharm.2004.12.030>
- Garud, A., Singh, D., & Garud, N. (2012). Solid Lipid Nanoparticles (SLN): Method, Characterization and Applications. *International Current Pharmaceutical Journal*, 1, 384-393. <https://doi.org/10.3329/ICPJ.V1I11.12065>
- Harde, H., Das, M., & Jain, S. (2011). Solid lipid nanoparticles: an oral bioavailability enhancer vehicle. *Expert opinion on drug delivery*, 8(11), 1407–1424. <https://doi.org/10.1517/17425247.2011.604311>
- Hu, F. Q., Yuan, H., Zhang, H. H., & Fang, M. (2002). Preparation of solid lipid nanoparticles with clobetasol propionate by a novel solvent diffusion method in aqueous system and physicochemical characterization. *International journal of pharmaceuticals*, 239(1-2), 121–128. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0378-5173\(02\)00081-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0378-5173(02)00081-9)
- Hu, L., Xing, Q., Meng, J., & Shang, C. (2010). Preparation and enhanced oral bioavailability of cryptotanshinone-loaded solid lipid nanoparticles. *AAPS PharmSciTech*, 11(2), 582–587. <https://doi.org/10.1208/s12249-010-9410-3>
- Khan, S., Tiwari, T., Tyagi, S., Bhowmik, M., Joshi, A., & Dubey, B. (2012). Preformulation studies and preparation of dithranol loaded solid lipid nanoparticles. *International journal of research and development in pharmacy and life sciences*, 1(4), 183-188.
- Mehnert, W., & Mäder, K. (2001). Solid lipid nanoparticles: production, characterization and applications. *Advanced drug delivery reviews*, 47(2-3), 165–196. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0169-409x\(01\)00105-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0169-409x(01)00105-3)
- Mukherjee, S., Ray, S., & Thakur, R. S. (2009). Solid lipid nanoparticles: a modern formulation approach in drug delivery system. *Indian journal of pharmaceutical sciences*, 71(4), 349–358. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0250-474X.57282>
- Mulla, J.S., Khazi, I.M., Sharma, N.K., Hiremath, S.P., & Jamakandi, V.G. (2011). Solid lipid nanoparticles: methods of preparation. *Indian Journal of Novel Drug delivery*, 3(3), 170-175.
- Müller, R. H., Radtke, M., & Wissing, S. A. (2002). Nanostructured lipid matrices for improved microencapsulation of drugs. *International journal of pharmaceuticals*, 242(1-2), 121–128. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0378-5173\(02\)00180-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0378-5173(02)00180-1)

- Narala, A., & Veerabrahma, K. (2013). Preparation, Characterization and Evaluation of Quetiapine Fumarate Solid Lipid Nanoparticles to Improve the Oral Bioavailability. *Journal of pharmaceuticals*, 2013, 265741. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2013/265741>
- Olbrich, C., Kayser, O., & Müller, R. (2002). Enzymatic Degradation of Dynasan 114 SLN – Effect of Surfactants and Particle Size. *Journal of Nanoparticle Research*, 4, 121-129. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1020159331420>
- Pardeike, J., Hommos, A., & Müller, R. H. (2009). Lipid nanoparticles (SLN, NLC) in cosmetic and pharmaceutical dermal products. *International journal of pharmaceuticals*, 366(1-2), 170–184. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpharm.2008.10.003>
- Suresh, G., Manjunath, K., Venkateswarlu, V., & Satyanarayana, V. (2007). Preparation, characterization, and in vitro and in vivo evaluation of lovastatin solid lipid nanoparticles. *AAPS PharmSciTech*, 8(1), 24. <https://doi.org/10.1208/pt0801024>
- Uner, M., & Yener, G. (2007). Importance of solid lipid nanoparticles (SLN) in various administration routes and future perspectives. *International journal of nanomedicine*, 2(3), 289–300.
- Xie, S., Zhu, L., Dong, Z., Wang, Y., Wang, X., & Zhou, W. (2011). Preparation and evaluation of ofloxacin-loaded palmitic acid solid lipid nanoparticles. *International journal of nanomedicine*, 6, 547–555. <https://doi.org/10.2147/IJN.S17083>
- Yang, S. C., Lu, L. F., Cai, Y., Zhu, J. B., Liang, B. W., & Yang, C. Z. (1999). Body distribution in mice of intravenously injected camptothecin solid lipid nanoparticles and targeting effect on brain. *Journal of controlled release : official journal of the Controlled Release Society*, 59(3), 299–307. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0168-3659\(99\)00007-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0168-3659(99)00007-3)